

ISic1393

I.Sicily inscription 1393

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140900

1. [έ]πί Ἡρακλείου τοῦ Α[—]-
2. [—]ο[υ] Ἀριστονίκου
3. Διὶ Ὠρίῳ ἀνφιπολεύσας
4. [Ἄρ] τῆμισκος Νύμ[φ]ωνος
5. Κάβαμος {²⁷Κάβα[λλ]ος}²⁷ ἐκ τῶν αὐτοῦ.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493008

EDCS 39101520

PHI 140900

Bibliography

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